

Impact of Self-efficacy On Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT: The present study is an attempt to study the impact of self-efficacy on academic achievement of senior secondary school students. A sample of 400 (200 male and 200 female) senior secondary school students from four districts of the state of Haryana was taken on the basis of multi-stage random sampling. Self-Efficacy Scale by Mathur and Bhatnagar (2012) and academic achievement scores from 10th class results were used to collect the data. Mean, Standard Deviation, and 't' test were used to analyse the data. It was observed from the present study that female students had more academic achievement than their male counterpart. It was found that academic achievement of senior secondary school students with high self-efficacy shows that had more academic achievement than those senior secondary school students with low self-efficacy. The present study will be very helpful to the educational planners, policy makers, administrators, teacher-educators and parents in particular and society in general in bringing about improvement in various skills of the teachers by strengthening their Self-Efficacy to boost academic achievement among students.

Key words: Academic achievement, self-efficacy, male, female senior secondary school students

Introduction

The importance of academic achievement has raised several important questions for educational researchers: What factors promote achievement in students? How far the different factors contribute towards academic achievement? Many factors have been hypothesized and researched upon. Researchers have come out with varied results, at times complementing each other, but at times contradicting each other. A complete and comprehensive picture of academic achievement still seems to elude the researchers. The search therefore continues. Educational researchers all over the world are still seeking a breakthrough in clarifying the phenomenon. It is especially so in countries like India, where the population growth has over shot the process of tapping in the natural resources and has out-stripped the expansion of facilities, consequently, heightening the competition for admission and promotion of the students to the next class. As a natural consequence, the intensity of increasing educational needs have not met with the needed facilities. This lag between educational requirement and the means to accomplish them has resulted in sharp decline in academic standards. The problems of deteriorating standards have forced the educationist to thoroughly probe the factors that affect the pupils' academic achievement in schools at all levels and on that basis to suggest measures for improvement to the educational authorities. It is this particular aspect of these studies that compelled the present investigators to study some of the psycho- social variables namely personality, intelligence and socio-economic background in relation to academic achievement of high, average

and low achievers so that the causes of poor academic performance may be treated out and be controlled suitably. Academic achievement plays an important role in the life of an individual because it gives may towards his goal. It is according to his academic achievement that he chooses his vocation, his career and his profession. In educational life academic achievement is highly valued. In the modern age, success in competition has become very important and essential to get a place in a higher institution. It has also been noticed that those who have better academic achievement, they are placed high in the Society. But it does mean that all the high academic achievers are highly positioned. The educational institutions occupy a very important and vital place in the educational environment of the people. The process of educational instruction in the educational institution is measured by the various periodical tests like weekly test, Monthly test, half yearly test and annual test. Whether the Student has achieved the knowledge imparted to him is being justified by the result he achieved from the tests. The results of achievement tests that measure relative accomplishment in a specific area of work can be termed as academic achievement

Objectives

- 1, To compare the academic achievement of male and female senior secondary school students.
2. To compare the academic achievement of senior secondary school students having high and low levels of self-efficacy.

Hypotheses

- 1, There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of male and female senior secondary school students.

2. There exists no significant difference in academic achievement of senior secondary school students having high and low levels of self-efficacy.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is defined as a person's belief about one's ability to organize and execute the course of action necessary to achieve a goal. In other words, persons with strong efficacy beliefs are more confident in their capacity to execute a behavior pattern. Beliefs about Self-efficacy have a significant impact on our goals and emotional reactions. Higher Self-efficacy is also associated with more persistence, a trait that allows one to gain corrective experiences that reinforce our sense of Self-efficacy. Self-efficacy refers to the confidence people have in their abilities that they will be successful at a given task. Individuals who possess a high degree of Self-efficacy are more likely to attempt challenging tasks, to persist longer at them, and to put more effort in the process. If highly efficacious individuals fail, they attribute the outcome to lack of effort or an adverse environment. When they succeed, they credit their achievement to their abilities. Self-efficacy is the people's belief about their capabilities to produce a designated level of performance that exercises influence over events that affect their lives. In functional terms Bandura (1986) suggested that efficacy expectations may predict whether or not one's action will be initiated, the amount of effort expended in pursuit of that activity, and the level of persistence in the 'face of obstacles'. Thus, Self-efficacy ultimately determines how an individual behaves, thinks and becomes motivated to be involved with particular roles. It also reflects students' judgment of capability to accomplish specific tasks. Self-efficacy is related to how much effort individuals will exert and how long they will persist in the face of obstacles. People with a weak sense of Self-Efficacy are more likely to reduce or abandon their efforts in the fact of difficulty or initial failure, whereas those with a strong sense of Self-Efficacy are more likely to extend greater effort and persist longer in that effort when faced with difficulty or initial failure. People will be more inclined to take on a task if they believe that they can succeed. People generally avoid tasks where their Self-efficacy is low, but will engage in tasks where their Self-efficacy is high. People with high Self-efficacy in a task are more likely to make more of an effort and persist longer than those with low Self-efficacy. Bandura showed that people of differing Self-efficacy are generally of the opinion that they are in control of their own life; that their own actions and decisions shape their

lives. On the other hand, people with low Self-efficacy may see their lives as somewhat out of their hands. Self-efficacy influences how individuals think and react emotionally to others and their environment. A strong sense of efficacy enhances human accomplishment and personal well-being in many ways. People with high assurance in their capabilities approach difficult tasks as challenges to be mastered rather than as threats to be avoided. Such an efficacious outlook fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in activities. They set themselves to challenging goals and maintain strong commitment to them. They heighten and sustain their efforts in the face of failure. They quickly recover their sense of efficacy after failures or setbacks. They attribute failure to insufficient effort or deficient knowledge and skills which are acquirable. They approach threatening situations with assurance that they can exercise control over them. Such an efficacious outlook produces personal accomplishments, reduces stress and lowers vulnerability to depression.

Review of Literature

Shkullaku (2013) conducted a study on gender difference in self-efficacy and academic performance among 180 Albanian students from two different universities. Results revealed a significant difference between male and female self-efficacy. **Singh & Katlana (2015)** explored the level of self-efficacy of male and female teachers of colleges and the analysis of the result pointed that there was significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female teachers of university. **Wang et al. (2015)** demonstrate that twice exceptional students could possess high-academic self-concept and academic self-efficacy that empower their academic success. **Ahuja (2016)** found that girls had statistically significant higher scores in self-efficacy, educational aspiration and academic achievement than boys. A statistically significant positive correlation was found between self-efficacy & educational aspiration, self-efficacy & academic achievement and educational aspiration & academic achievement of secondary school students. **Bhagat and Baliya (2016)** also found an insignificant difference was found in the self-efficacy of secondary school students in relation to their gender and academic achievement. **Marsudi (2017)** showed that self-efficacy and academic achievement had positive and significant influence on performance, while perceived organizational support strengthened the influence on performance of the lecturers of "A" accredited private universities. **Hasan and Parvez (2019)** resulted in a significant positive correlation between self-efficacy and

academic achievement. Moreover, self-efficacy reported no significant differential effect on academic achievement. Gender was reported to have a significant differential effect on self-efficacy. However, gender and locale were also found to have significant differential effects on the academic achievement of secondary school students. **Odame-Mensaw (2019)** revealed that respondents had positive self-efficacy. Further, analysis showed that self-efficacy significantly predicted academic achievement, while girls were found to have more academic achievement than boys. . **AlAjmi and AlAzemi (2021)** indicated a statistically significant positive correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement of the study sample. Also, there were apparent differences between arithmetic means in academic self-efficacy in all variables where they were statistically significant only according to the academic average.

Justification of the Study

A person's self-efficacy is a person's opinion that he or she is capable of effectively completing a particular task, and it has a significant impact on people's behavior (Bandura, 1977). As a result, students' academic achievement is greatly influenced by their self-efficacy. In addition to self-efficacy, students' academic success is best predicted by their level of academic achievement. It was found in the literature of many existing researchers that self-efficacy had an instrumental role in determining the level of a student's academic achievement. Hence, an attempt has been made to study the impact of self-efficacy on academic achievement of senior school students. .

Statement of the Problem

Table: 1, Mean score, standard deviation and ‘t’ value of academic achievement of male and female senior secondary students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Male students	400	73.46	11.44	6.705**
Female students	400	79.11	12.41	

Table 1 indicates that the mean scores of academic achievement among male and female senior secondary school students. It indicates that the mean scores of male and female students on academic achievement are 73.46 and 79.11 respectively. The ‘t’ value comes out to be (6.705) which is significant at 0.01Level concluding that male and female students differ significantly on

Table 2, Mean score, standard deviation and ‘t’ value of academic achievement of senior secondary school students having low and high self-efficacy

Types of Home environment	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Low self-efficacy	208	64.67	10.525	20.037**
High self-efficacy	437	83.66	8.182	

*Significant at 0.01 level

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Methodology

Descriptive research is concerned with hypothesis formulation and testing and the analysis or relationship between non-manipulated variables and the development of generalizations. In this study, a Descriptive research method has been used.

Population and Sample of the Study

The study aims at describing the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in relation to their self-efficacy. It, therefore, requires that data to be collected from the concerned categories of senior secondary school students, who form the population of the study, On the basis of multi-stage random sampling. In the present study, 800 (400 male and 300 female) senior secondary students from four districts of the state of Haryana will form the sample.

Tools Used

1. Self-Efficacy Test by Vikas Sharma (2018)
2. Academic Achievement Test scores have been taken from the academic performance of students in previous examinations.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The Mean, Standard Deviation, ‘t’ test and Karl Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient Correlation were used to analyze the data.

Data Analysis

The principal objective of the present paper is to see the impact of self-efficacy on academic achievement among senior secondary school students of Haryana. The difference in academic achievement in relation to gender and level of self-efficacy achievement are shown in Table 1 to Table 2

academic achievement. As a result, the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in academic achievements of male and female the senior secondary school students” is not retained. The higher mean score of female students shows that they had more academic achievement than their counterpart male students.

Table 2 indicates that the mean scores of academic achievement among senior secondary school students in relation to their self-efficacy. It indicates that the mean scores academic achievement of senior secondary school students having low and high self-efficacy are 64.67 and 83.66 respectively. The 't' value comes out to be (20.037) which is significant at 0.01 Level concluding that senior secondary school students with low and high self-efficacy differ significantly on academic achievement. As a result, the null hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in academic achievement of senior secondary school students having high and low self-efficacy" is not retained. The higher mean score of students having high self-efficacy shows that they had more academic achievement than those students with low self-efficacy.

Findings of the Study

1. There exists a significant difference in the level of academic achievement of male and female senior secondary school students. The higher mean score of female students showed that they had more academic achievement than their male counterpart.
2. There exists a significant difference in the level of academic achievement of senior secondary school students having high and low levels of self-efficacy. The higher mean score of academic achievement of senior secondary school students with high self-efficacy shows that they are more achievement motivated than those senior secondary school students with low self-efficacy.

Discussion of Results

The present paper highlighted girl's superiority over boy students in relation to academic achievement. The present finding is supported by **Ahuja (2016)** and **Odame-Mensaw (2019)** revealed that girls were found to have more academic achievement than boys. In the present study, it was found that academic achievement of senior secondary school students with high self-efficacy shows that they are more achievement motivated than those senior secondary school students with low self-efficacy. The finding of the present research is supported by Bandura and Cervone (1986), **Marsudi (2017)** and **AlAjmi and AlAzemi (2021)** who stated that a low sense of self-efficacy should be associated with negative achievement behaviors (e.g., low effort and persistence). The present study will be very helpful to the educational planners, policy makers, administrators, teacher-educators and parents in particular and society in general in bringing about improvement in various skills of the teachers by

strengthening their Self-Efficacy to boost academic performance among students.

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